

AI-Enhanced Detection, Localization, and Vulnerability Assessment of Jamming and Spoofing for Safety-Critical Users

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Zenodo Community	PNT2026
Record Type	Conference Preprint
DOI	Assigned upon approval (placeholder)
License	CC-BY 4.0
Keywords	Spoofing, jamming, detection, angle-of-arrival, AI
Funding	This work has been partially funded by the European Space Agency (ESA) NAVISP Element 2 – Competitiveness in PNT initiative

Abstract

Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) can affect both civil and military users and poses a particularly serious threat to safety-critical applications such as aviation, maritime navigation, financial systems, and telecommunications. Moreover, the steady rise in interference events over the recent years demands the development of solutions to counteract their effects. To address this challenge, this paper presents the SILENT and VAULT product concepts, developed under the ESA NAVISP Element 2 initiative, and designed to detect and localize RFI, with the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) models to boost the performance.

SILENT nodes are monitoring stations built with commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components and a custom signal processing chain. SILENT nodes can be deployed either as a permanent installation or on mobile platforms given the optimized size, weight and power (SWaP). Each node incorporates an array of four antennas to estimate the angle-of-arrival of GNSS signals, both in azimuth and elevation, for the L1/E1 and L5/E5 bands. This is achieved through analysis of the signal pseudorange and carrier phase between pairs of antennas, and any clustering of signals in the double differences domain is flagged as spoofing. The decision is supported by additional layers of detection, including analysis of the receiver's automatic gain control (AGC) and the signal's carrier-to-noise density ratio (C/N_0). All these layers utilize the observables from a COTS GNSS receiver

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and the performance is shown to be comparable to high-grade RFI monitoring systems. Additionally, a wideband spectrum monitoring function is integrated.

Similarly, VAULT tool is a server-side application to which SILENT nodes may connect for additional analysis. It can combine data from multiple SILENT nodes to localize the RFI source using a technique that fuses power-difference-of-arrival (PDOA) and angle-of-arrival measurements. Once a source is geolocated, an assessment of the impact of the RFI is performed using RF propagation techniques that consider digital elevation models (DEM) such that the afflicted service volume can be bounded. Moreover, two built-in AI methods are incorporated, namely a support vector machine (SVM) classification module and a variational autoencoder (VAE) model with the possibility for the user to retrain the models with newly collected data. A graphical user interface (GUI) is available for node configuration and visualization of all relevant system data.

SILENT and VAULT product concepts have been put to the test at the Jammertest 2025 event against jamming and both coherent and incoherent spoofing attacks. Two stationary mounted SILENT nodes were deployed. All detection layers correctly identified the presence of jamming and spoofing attacks, and the determination of angle-of-arrival worked as expected. Similarly, both SVM and VAE methods performed well, demonstrating that these techniques can be successfully applied to real-time RFI detection. However, the limitation of using two nodes only resulted in a moderate localization accuracy of the spoofing source. Nevertheless, the results obtained by the SILENT and VAULT operational models presented in this paper show that a cost-effective, COTS-built network of monitoring stations can be a feasible solution against the increasing problem of RFI.

Keywords: GNSS, RFI, spoofing, jamming, detection, localization, angle-of-arrival, PDOA, AI, SVM, classification, VAE, COTS, aviation, spectrum monitoring

1 Introduction

Protection of safety-critical infrastructure from GNSS Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) is a vast topic with different commercial solutions already available in the market [1], [2], [3]. At the core, a monitoring function performs constant checks of the GNSS signals of interest, normally civilian GNSS signals. Depending on the capabilities, a detection function determines whether a jamming or spoofing event is taking place, and a characterization (classification) of it may be performed. Moreover, most of them make use of many antennas for localization purposes. An alert is typically generated automatically by the system and visualized in a human-machine interface (HMI) for operators to take action. These solutions are typically permanent installations, with portable versions with reduced capabilities in some cases, that have very expensive development costs associated (in the order of millions of euro in some cases) and lack flexibility as customer requirements may change once the system is deployed and operational. At the other end, solutions such as handheld spectrum analyzers with direction-finding capabilities [4] cope with some of the caveats of the previous systems but with limited coverage, requiring human intervention and interpretation of the measurements.

This paper presents an innovative, cost-efficient solution to RFI monitoring to be mounted as a permanent installation or to be used as a portable station. Different detection layers are implemented in the sensing nodes that utilize GNSS observables from (but not limited to) L1/E1 and L5/E5 signals obtained from COTS receivers, and make use of traditional signal processing and modern AI-based techniques for the detection and localization of both jamming and spoofing. Moreover, an angle-of-arrival estimate can be retrieved with as few as 3 receivers using a co-planar antenna array layout with the baselines few meters (less than 3 m) apart.

The addition of an extra antenna element is done for obtaining a 3D angle-of-arrival. A processing tool centralizes the information from all RFI monitoring nodes to provide a more accurate localization by combining the different angle-of-arrival estimates and performing a modified power differences of arrival (PDOA). Finally, an assessment of the localized threat is automatically triggered as soon as the nodes report it. This assessment is performed in terms of RF received power at different altitudes and ground locations taking into account a detailed digital elevation model with its associated RF propagation phenomena. With this analysis in place, safety-critical users could e.g., determine the afflicted service volumes easily. The performance of the system has been evaluated with both simulated data and in a real world scenario, namely the Jammertest 2025 event.

This paper is organized as follows: [Section 2](#) introduces already existing RFI monitoring solutions using COTS components. Next, [Section 3](#) overviews the impact of RFI on safety-critical applications. Typical tools for the assessment of the impact of RFI are briefly reviewed. In [Section 4](#), the developed system is explained, namely the SILENT and VAULT product concepts. [Section 5](#) details the algorithms used for the purpose of detection, localization and impact assessment, including the AI methods implemented for detection of jamming and spoofing. Finally, the validation and verification results of the system are presented in [Section 6](#), where a first in-lab phase using simulated and conducted RFI was followed by an open-field test campaign at the Jammertest 2025 event.

2 RFI Monitoring Systems Using COTS GNSS Receivers

Clearly, RFI detection techniques may vary in complexity, effectiveness and robustness against specific extrinsic conditions such as the geometry of the attacker with respect to the RFI monitoring system, attack sophistication or platform dynamics when mounted on a vehicle. Moreover, the performance of the RFI monitoring system is tightened not only to the implemented detection techniques but also to the hardware architecture. Indeed, most commercially available RFI monitoring systems employ specific hardware for the digital processing function (e.g., FPGAs or SoCs), third-party IP cores onboard these logic units, custom-built RF components such as the antennas and their radomes, or ad hoc mechanical fixtures for housing the electronics. Such dependencies can lead to increased costs, longer development cycles and a limitation in system's scalability, customization and modernization as the GNSS threats evolve in a much fast-paced context.

However, there is a trend towards more affordable and easy-to-deploy RFI monitoring systems that balance the limitations of employing inexpensive hardware (i.e., GNSS receivers, antennas and computing modules) with their intent to be ubiquitous and scalable for wide-area protection. As an example, the work in [5] presents a GNSS Integrity Monitoring Station (GIMS) that uses a low-cost Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) receiver (SIRfIII Star GPS, now part of Qualcomm) for integrity purposes. The observables from the receiver are combined with integrity data from the SISNeT network (now part of the EGNOS Data Access Service, EDAS) and a Receiver Autonomous Integrity Monitoring (RAIM) algorithm to compute a Horizontal Protection Level (HPL) which guarantees that the Position Error (PE) is bounded with a certain probability. Conversely, the RFI monitoring function is based on a statistical test that utilizes power spectrum density values obtained from a Software-Defined Radio (SDR).

Similarly, the authors in [6] propose a GNSS integrity monitoring solution based on quickest detection theory such that the time-to-alarm or detection delay is minimized. The CUSUM algorithm [7] is applied to RFI detection and it is based on changes in the power of the received

signal. The underlying assumption is that this simple metric can be obtained from receivers with low computational capabilities such as in smartphones. More concisely, a statistical metric is defined that relates the received power of a snapshot with the noise power, which can be estimated. This statistical metric is assumed Gaussian with known mean and variance for both clean (before) and RFI (after) conditions, and they are derived from the central limit theorem. Thus, the CUSUM algorithm with its associated log-likelihood ratio can be analytically solved. The results are based on simulated experiments and they show promising detection delay (in number of samples) for relatively low values of interference-to-noise ratios.

Related to the previous, the work in [8] introduces a low-cost COTS GNSS RFI detection and classification system. The latter is implemented using Machine Learning (ML). Features from both a GNSS receiver and an SDR are pre-processed for two distinct ML architectures, namely a random forest for classification purposes of time-series data like C/N_0 , AGC and elevation, and ResNet, a deep learning approach that utilizes spectrogram images. Moreover, a network of few nodes are installed in a controlled environment to mimic a typical two-lane motorway such that a localization of the interference is performed. Results show that the proposed characterization framework performs very well in terms of accuracy and classification.

More recently, the StanfordGPS Lab has proposed a low-cost GNSS RFI monitoring system for protecting critical infrastructures such as airports using COTS GNSS receivers [9]. The envisioned purpose of this development is to deploy a dense network of RFI monitoring systems in e.g., many international, domestic and regional airports in the US, at a relatively low cost and with reasonable detection performance. The authors utilize the observables from a COTS receiver, a u-blox F9P, to detect both jamming and spoofing. More precisely, power-based metrics such as satellite C/N_0 values and receiver's Automatic Gain Control (AGC) are thoroughly characterized, implemented and evaluated for the selected COTS GNSS receiver considering, e.g., the temperature drift in the RF chain and other internal gain adjustments. Moreover, an accurate (absolute) received power level for repeatable and comparable performance is derived from an uncalibrated RF spectrum representation computed by the receiver. The amplitude levels relative to the full scale are translated to power measurements in dBW/Hz facilitating the determination of thresholds and power level masks as defined in Minimum Operation Performance Standards (MOPS).

The proposed method is validated using real world conditions with remarkable good sensitivity, specificity and accuracy values for classification of jamming and spoofing attacks. However, as the authors point out, the internal anti-spoofing mechanisms of the COTS GNSS receiver may difficult the classification task for some scenarios. Moreover, despite the use of the more constant receiver power from SBAS satellites due to the geostationary orbit, the proposed method requires adjustments for different receiver locations (longitude dependency). In addition, deviations in the performance of the proposed method due to batch production processes of the selected COTS GNSS receiver and antenna are not evaluated.

3 Impact of RFI on Safety-Critical Users

The impact of RFI has gained awareness beyond specialized research groups and their consequences are not limited to GNSS service providers and users. Moreover, the ever-growing dependency of some safety-critical applications on GNSS such as area navigation (RNAV) in aviation, autonomous driving, assisted docking in maritime technology or construction automation requires an extra layer of protection such that the condition of these services is within its mandated operational requirements and prescribed limits. By contrast, any disruption –

intentional or unintentional— may result not only in safety risks for the people, equipment and environment involved, but also in viral media content with large consequences at political, economic and technological level.

3.1 Tools for Assessment of Impact of RFI

Different tools for the assessment of the impact of RFI to users and service volumes of e.g., airspace, exist. Typically RF propagation tools with different modeling assumptions are used. As an example, a simple free-space propagation model with radio horizon computation for improved impact accuracy over the horizon is assumed by EUROCONTROL's guidelines for interference testing [10]. More recently, EUROCONTROL has published a GNSS Threat Assessment Tool that qualitatively assesses the risk of PBN-based operations using pre-defined RFI scenarios [11].

Although not intended for GNSS RFI specifically, commercially available solutions for wireless radio planning may be utilized for the purpose of quantifying RF propagation in complex, wide-area scenarios. Tools for radio (e.g., radar) coverage may compute ground-to-ground and ground-to-air coverage considering digital terrain models with very high resolution and fidelity [12]. The received signal in a discretized terrain may be obtained from numerical analysis for identifying RF propagation effects such as reflection and refraction identifying afflicted service volumes easily.

3.2 Case Study: Aviation

Aviation stands out as the most demanding transport in terms of safety. The uniform implementation of regulations, practices and safety programs by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) guarantees that highest levels of operational safety across the industry. As an example, the application of area navigation (RNAV) techniques in all flight phases contributes to a greater flight efficiency and a more optimized available airspace. The closely related concept of Performance Based Navigation (PBN) facilitates the implementation of these air navigation operations with different levels of spacing, performance and navigation aids to be used depending on the specification [13].

While the initial intention was to use GNSS as the primary navigation infrastructure in PBN procedures, the European Commission Implementing Regulation 2018/1048 of July 2018 now requires the Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) to have contingency measures in order to ensure that navigation services are maintained through other means when, e.g., GNSS are no longer available or degraded [14]. Clearly, this is the case when GNSS systems are subject to intentional or unintentional jamming and spoofing events. While at first glance these events may be unlikely or subject of study and concern of very specialized groups and organizations, recent events of intentional jamming targeting high-profile executives (e.g., [15]) has prompted a general-audience debate and awareness of the topic.

Throughout this paper we will consider the use case of aviation for the purpose of assessing the impact of RFI to a safety-critical application. The quantification of the impacted service volume is done by computing the RFI received power at different flight levels (FLs) over the airways of interest in a specific region. This methodology could be extrapolated to other domains easily.

4 SILENT and VAULT Product Concepts

The system presented in this paper is comprised of two parts: the SILENT nodes and the VAULT tool that can work together or independently of each other.

SILENT (Spoofing Identification and Localization for Enhanced Navigation and Timing) nodes are in charge of GNSS bands monitoring and the initial computation to determine whether the node is being afflicted by RFI. The collected information is sent in near real-time to the VAULT tool for further processing and reporting (Figure 1). The low SWaP of the nodes allows them to be either stationary (i.e., as a permanent installation) or portable. More precisely:

- The system comprises up to 4 GNSS antennas for localization purposes with a spacing of as few as 3 meters (Figure 2). Longer baselines could be employed for improved angle-of-arrival accuracy and better observables de-correlation. Moreover, localization can be done selecting one of three modes: 2D mode (L1-only, azimuth-only), 2.5D mode (dual frequency L1/E1 and L5/E5 bands, azimuth-only) and 3D mode (dual frequency L1/E1 and L5/E5 bands, azimuth and elevation).
- The system performs the GNSS monitoring of the civilian bands from GPS, Galileo, GLONASS, BeiDou and QZSS, including L1C/A, L5, E1-B/C and E5a. The monitoring function reports signal parameters such as average C/N_0 , minimum and maximum Doppler shift, pseudorange and carrier phase metrics, percentage of cycle slips, receiver-specific parameters such as AGC level, constellation parameters (azimuth, elevation) and PVT information.
- The previous GNSS monitoring function is complemented by a spectrum monitoring function. A wideband spectrum snapshot is available every 5 seconds that spans from 1 to 2 GHz. Refresh rate as well as frequency span are configurable since this task is allocated to a dedicated SDR receiver. Secondly, an in-band spectrum representation is obtained at a rate of 1 Hz and it spans 150 MHz around the upper and lower GNSS bands (i.e., L1/E1 and L5/E5, resp.). In all cases, channel integrated power (for L1/E1 and L5/E5) is computed and visualized separately for operator awareness of unintentional spectrum content in these bands.
- Finally, a health monitoring subsystem is implemented such that environmental variables (indoor/outdoor temperature, wind speed and direction, humidity, rain rate, etc.) are monitored as well.

The VAULT (Vulnerability Assessment and Understanding the impact of Localized GNSS Threats) tool is a server-side application that gathers the information from all SILENT nodes, stores it, and carries out a more detailed analysis to determine the RFI type (jamming or spoofing), the localization of the transmitter position, the attack reach and the afflicted flight procedures and service volume. In addition, it allows the user to analyze and audit past results, monitor the SILENT nodes health status, and change their configuration remotely.

On the other hand, VAULT incorporates not only an accurate geolocation module that utilizes power differences of arrival (PDOA) and angle-of-arrival information from different SILENT nodes, but also AI methods, namely a Support Vector Machine (SVM) module for classification purposes and (Section 5.6.1) a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) module for anomaly detection (Section 5.6.2).

As a part of the VAULT product concept, a Human-Machine Interface (HMI) has been developed for the users to interact with the system. It is the interactive, operator-centric part of

Figure 1: Diagram showing SILENT nodes (in red) and VAULT tool. The cost effectiveness of SILENT nodes may facilitate the rapid and massive deployment of them across wide areas.

the system, and it has been developed to allow for the complete system management including detailed analysis, reporting, auditing and archive operations. The landing page (Figure 3) shows a map of the area of interest with the location of the deployed SILENT nodes. An overlay containing the flight procedures is included. In addition, the user can also navigate to each SILENT node specific page view.

The events detected by the system are shown on a sidebar on the left and the user can select them to show their details such as position, time span, stations that detected it, and the afflicted flight procedures. The map view also updates to represent visually this information.

The first other view is the SILENT node view (Figure 4) and it is the most useful for deep analysis of the received data during an event, as well as for general signals monitoring during nominal conditions. It shows node-specific information starting from the node's latest health and weather data and the latest PVT solution. The solution is shown both numerically and on a map, showing also the configured calibrated position of the station to easily compare the two.

5 Spoofing Detection and Localization

For detection and localization purposes, SILENT exploits the geometric correlations of the carrier phase and/or pseudorange across the baselines. More precisely, the detection of spoofed signals is based on the so-called Dispersion of Double Differences (D3) [16]. This technique is used for detecting GNSS spoofing attacks by analyzing the dispersion of double differences in carrier phase (or pseudorange) measurements from a dual-antenna setup. Indeed, the presence of a single-source spoofer will indicate a concentration in the double differences domain. The set of test hypotheses is given by [17]:

Figure 2: Computer-aided design of a SILENT node. The top H-shaped structure contains the actual components from SILENT, while the lattice structure is included to illustrate the integration on e.g., a frangible mast. The displayed model shows a signaling beacon and a weather station for environmental monitoring in remote deployments.

Figure 3: Events view and inspection.

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_0 : \exists (i, j, k) \in (S \cup A) : & \begin{cases} |\mu_i - \mu_k|^2 \leq \xi_k^2, \\ |\mu_j - \mu_k|^2 \leq \xi_k^2 \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \\
 H_1 : \forall (i, j, k) \in (S \cup A) : & \begin{cases} |\mu_i - \mu_k|^2 > \xi_k^2, \\ |\mu_j - \mu_k|^2 > \xi_k^2 \end{cases} \quad \text{or}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where H_0 is the null hypothesis that reads that at least 3 counterfeit satellites i , j and k from the ensemble of possible spoofed (S) and authentic (A) signals are closely related in terms of their double difference mean μ . H_1 is the alternate hypothesis that states the opposite. The term ξ_k^2 can be regarded as a threshold that shall balance the probability of missed detection and false alarm. It relates to the variance of the noise of the double differences as explained in [16]. In addition to that, estimation of the Doppler frequency is performed to detect cycle slips in the carrier phase, which may assist the system to detect spoofed signals.

For determination of the angle-of-arrival, single differences (SD) are exploited instead. They could be understood as the projection of the line of sight vector of each satellite onto the baseline vector. The implemented algorithm is based on the Precise and Fast (P&F) algorithm

Figure 4: SILENT node view.

[18]. More formally, the pseudorange and carrier phase SD between the reference antenna j and i are given by:

$$\Delta\rho_{ij}^m = \mathbf{g}_{ij}^T \mathbf{x}^m + c\Delta t_{ij} + \Delta l_b + \Delta\epsilon_\rho \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta\phi_{ij}^m = \mathbf{g}_{ij}^T \mathbf{x}^m + c\Delta t_{ij} + \Delta l_b + \lambda\Delta N_{ij}^m + \Delta\epsilon_\phi \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}^m = (x^m, y^m, z^m)^T$ is the angle-of-arrival vector of the satellite m , $\mathbf{g}_{ij} = (g_{ij,x}^m, g_{ij,y}^m, g_{ij,z}^m)^T$ is the baseline vector of the antenna, λ , the wavelength of the carrier, N_{ij}^m is the (carrier-phase) integer ambiguity, Δt_{ij} is the error due to the receiver clock, Δl_b is the error term due to RF frontend hardware elements such as cables and antennas, $\Delta\epsilon$ is the error term due to the SD operation, and c is the speed of light.

On the one hand, it is observed that SD do not eliminate errors due to the receiver clock and the hardware elements of the RF frontend. A mechanism to solve the first is through the use of an external clock reference that synchronizes the pair of receivers. However, some COTS receivers limit this possibility (no external clock reference input is available) and the observables shall be synchronized differently. This is the case in SILENT nodes where the u-blox F9P observables had to be aligned and extrapolated to the same epoch using the sub-microsecond timestamp provided for each measurement and the measured receiver clock bias. Regarding the resolution of ambiguities (term $\lambda\Delta N_{ij}^m$), there are several existing methods to achieve this purpose. In our case, the LAMBDA method was used [19].

The following Sections explain the additional detection layers and algorithms that complement the previous spoofing detection and angle-of-arrival estimation. Moreover, Section 5.7 contains an algorithm that fuses the detection flags from all of them using a Bayesian framework.

5.1 AGC vs C/N_0

The methods for spoofing detection based on received power have had a rising presence in research in recent years due to their simplicity of implementation and the difficulty for a spoofer to evade. Either with direct in-band power measurements [20], or taking the receiver's AGC value as a proxy, the attacker would inevitably leave a noticeable imprint on the victim's received power, as mentioned by [21]. Even higher distortions will be present for overpowered attacks, used by the attacker to ensure the victim acquires and tracks their signal instead of the real GNSS signal-in-space.

While in-band power measurements require specific equipment, such as in SILENT nodes with the use of a dedicated SDR, the measurements of AGC are commonly available for commercial receivers. Taking the C/N_0 as a measurement of the signal's quality, the two can be combined to determine regions of nominal, jamming, and spoofing condition. The combination may be performed using:

- Individual C/N_0 for each satellite in the epoch [21].
- Maximum C/N_0 of all satellites in the epoch [22].
- Average C/N_0 of all satellites in the epoch.

The latter is the approach implemented in SILENT nodes' AGC vs C/N_0 module. The individual and maximum C/N_0 showed difficulty in early analysis when using u-blox F9P receivers due to the reported C/N_0 for the highest quality satellites barely dropping, or not dropping at all, for low-to-medium power jamming attacks, while the C/N_0 values in the rest of the satellite set were noticeably dropping as expected. Steady C/N_0 values with lower AGC caused by the jamming generated false spoofing alerts for all but the most high-power jamming attacks. However it was observed that the average C/N_0 value behaved much closer to the expected trend.

The implemented method requires a calibration with a period of nominal GNSS conditions, recommended of at least 1 hour and preferably for 24 hours. For each GNSS band, each epoch's AGC value (AGC) and C/N_0 average value ($C/N_{0,mean}$) is recorded. Then the mean of all values in the nominal period are computed as the calibration outputs: \overline{AGC} and $\overline{C/N_{0,mean}}$.

During monitoring, for each epoch the differences with respect to the calibrated values are obtained as follows:

$$\Delta AGC = AGC - \overline{AGC} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta C/N_{0,mean} = C/N_{0,mean} - \overline{C/N_{0,mean}} \quad (5)$$

A separating line is set by the user through configuration to determine the spoofing region from the nominal+jamming region, by specifying the X axis intercept $Line_{C/N_{0,mean}}$ and the slope $Line_{slope}$ (Figure 5). The spoofing decision is taken if the $(AGC, C/N_{0,mean})$ is to the right of the decision line in Figure 5:

$$\Delta AGC < (\Delta C/N_{0,mean} - Line_{C/N_{0,mean}}) \cdot Line_{slope} \quad (6)$$

Results have shown consistent detection of spoofing attacks with no false alerts nor miss detections for the tests carried out in laboratory, even with the 1 dB-Hz discretization of C/N_0 provided by the u-blox F9P receiver. However, further testing with a variety of jamming and spoofing power ranges and jamming types would be useful to confirm the detection capabilities of the method under a wide range of conditions.

5.2 C/N_0 vs Elevation

A different approach for RFI detection may consist in analyzing the signal's quality (C/N_0) against the expected value directly. SILENT nodes do this by implementing a C/N_0 vs elevation method as part of its redundant detection strategy, although this method can only be used to detect jamming.

Figure 5: Example of AGC vs $C/N_{0,mean}$ method for a high-power spoofing preceded by a high-power jamming. Red: nominal values previous to the attack. Orange: values corresponding to a jamming attack previous to the spoofing attack. Blue: spoofing. Green: nominal values after the attack.

The method consists in comparing the received C/N_0 of each satellite with an upper and lower quadratic curve that is a function of the satellite elevation. For each satellite, given the satellite's elevation (el_t) and carrier-to-noise density ratio $C/N_{0,t}$ reported at an epoch t , and the configurable coefficients set by the user a_0 , a_1 , and a_2 for the upper and lower curves, the upper and lower quadratic curves are given by:

$$C/N_{0,up} = a_{0,up} + a_{1,up}el_t + a_{2,up}el_t^2 \quad (7)$$

$$C/N_{0,down} = a_{0,down} + a_{1,down}el_t + a_{2,down}el_t^2 \quad (8)$$

The jamming decision is given when $C/N_{0,t} < C/N_{0,down}$ since a lower (effective) carrier-to-noise density ratio is expected [23]. Indeed, results show the expected quadratic behavior with elevation of the C/N_0 and a clear distinction between the nominal/spoofing case, and the jamming (Figure 6).

The per-satellite calibration may be computed by recording the $(C/N_0, el)$ of satellites during 24 hours of nominal period and forming a standard least squares system as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C/N_{0,1} \\ C/N_{0,2} \\ \vdots \\ C/N_{0,i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & el_1 & el_1^2 \\ 1 & el_2 & el_2^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & el_i & el_i^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \vdots \\ \varepsilon_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Or, in matrix form, $C = EA + \epsilon$, with the least squares solution given by $A = (E^T E)^{-1} E^T C$.

Figure 6: Example of C/N_0 vs elevation method for a high-power spoofing preceded by a high-power jamming. Red: nominal values previous to attack. Green: values corresponding to a jamming attack previous to the spoofing attack. Orange: values during spoofing. Blue: nominal values after the attack. The spoofing and nominal values after the attack at the bottom of the figure correspond to the acquisition phase of the signals.

5.3 Modified PDOA for RFI Localization

VAULT implements a precise localization module that combines angle-of-arrival information with received power measurements from different SILENT nodes. The latter are utilized in a PDOA localization algorithm. Indeed, angle-of-arrival (bearings) only information is fused using a total least squares (TLS) estimator. The problem is reduced to a two-dimensional localization problem where p is the location of a stationary target (i.e., the spoofer), and θ_k and r_k are the bearing angle and observer (SILENT node) positions, respectively, at time k , related by the nonlinear equation [24]:

$$\theta_k = \tan^{-1} \frac{\Delta y_k}{\Delta x_k}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta y_k = p_y - r_{y,k}$, $\Delta x_k = p_x - r_{x,k}$, $p = [p_x, p_y]^T$ and $r_k = [r_{x,k}, r_{y,k}]^T$. The target location p shall be estimated from a sequence of noisy bearing measurements $\tilde{\theta}_k = \theta_k + n_k$, where n_k is assumed white Gaussian noise with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{n_k}^2$.

A least squares (LS) solution to the problem above is given by:

$$\hat{p}_{LS} = \arg \min \|Ap - b\|_2^2 = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T b \quad (11)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_1^T \\ a_2^T \\ \vdots \\ a_N^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad b = \begin{bmatrix} a_1^T r_1 \\ a_2^T r_2 \\ \vdots \\ a_N^T r_N \end{bmatrix}, \quad \eta = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_1 \\ \eta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \eta_N \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$a_k = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \tilde{\theta}_k \\ -\cos \tilde{\theta}_k \end{bmatrix}, \quad \eta_k = d_k \sin n_k$$

where $d_k = \|s_k\|_2$ is the target range from the observer position r_k , and a_k is a unit vector orthogonal to the noisy bearing vector \tilde{s}_k such that $p = r_k + \tilde{s}_k + e_k$, $e_k^T \tilde{s}_k = 0$. The TLS estimate is obtained by computing first the augmented matrix $L [A, b]$ and obtaining its singular value decomposition (SVD):

$$\hat{p}_{\text{TLS}} = -\frac{1}{v_{33}} \begin{bmatrix} v_{13} \\ v_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where $v_3 = [v_{13}, v_{23}, v_{33}]^T$ is the right-most column vector from the right singular matrix V that results from the decomposition.

The TLS estimate is a first estimate of the position of the target p that combines the angle-of-arrival information from all SILENT nodes that have detected the spoofer. In addition, the perimeter of the intersecting polygon containing all angle-of-arrival estimates and uncertainties is also extracted. This perimeter is used as a mask in the potential PDOA locations to be evaluated during the optimization problem as it is explained below.

Traditionally, PDOA localization techniques employ relatively simple path loss models. Most of them assume a dependence on received signal power proportional to $d^{-\alpha}$, where α is the path loss exponent that may take values ranging from 2 (free-space model) to 6 depending on the environment. Moreover, the received signal power in dBm is given by:

$$P_r = P_0 - 10\alpha \log_{10} \left(\frac{d}{d_0} \right) \quad (13)$$

where P_0 is a reference power level at distance d_0 . Considering two SILENT nodes located at (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) . If the RFI emitter is located at (x, y) , the measured signal power in dBm at each SILENT node is given by:

$$P_k = P_0 - 10\alpha \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_k}{d_0} \right), \quad k = 1, 2 \quad (14)$$

where $d_k = \sqrt{(x - x_k)^2 + (y - y_k)^2}$. The power difference of these two power levels is given by:

$$P_{12} = P_1 - P_2 = 10\alpha \log_{10} \left(\frac{d_2}{d_1} \right) \quad (15)$$

If the actual measured power difference between the nodes is \bar{P}_{12} , the quantity

$$Q(x, y) = \left[\bar{P}_{12} - 5\alpha \log_{10} \left(\frac{(x - x_2)^2 + (y - y_2)^2}{(x - x_1)^2 + (y - y_1)^2} \right) \right] \quad (16)$$

shall be minimized for finding the optimal RFI emitter location (x, y) .

The derivation above is modified by assuming a pre-calculated attenuation (path loss) model. An attenuation map is precomputed for each fixed SILENT node as shown in [Figure 7](#). The underlying assumption is that the path loss is reciprocal, i.e., the path that a signal traverses is the same as seen from transmitter to receiver than from receiver to transmitter, whenever the antennas are assumed omnidirectional. Attenuation maps make use of digital elevation models in companion with the Irregular Terrain Model with Obstructions (ITWOM) model to improve

path loss prediction. More precisely, the ITWOM 3.0 model includes equations from the ITU-R P.1546 model to account for terrain and obstructions. The path loss maps are generated using the open-source tool SPLAT! [25].

Using the pre-loaded attenuation map, the PDOA method is modified as follows:

- The received signal power from Eq. (13) uses a discretized function for the attenuation as follows:

$$P_r = P_0 - f(d, d_0) \quad (17)$$

such that it evaluated the attenuation at a given point at distance d from d_0 (SILENT node location) in the map.

- A joint discrete probability density function (pdf) is defined over the complete analysis region such that geolocation estimate is the position in the defined grid of coordinates (n, m) where the value of this joint pdf is maximized, i.e.:

$$(n, m) = \arg \max_{(n,m)} \prod_{s=1}^S F_{XY}(s, n, m) \quad (18)$$

for $n = 1, \dots, N, m = 1, \dots, M$, and where $F_{XY}(s, n, m)$ is the pdf for a SILENT node at specific grid point.

Figure 7: Path loss map computed for a SILENT node. Axis represent latitude and longitude pixel dimensions. Latitude range is approximately 40 to 42 degrees north, longitude range 0 to 2 degrees east.

5.4 Validation of the Proposed Method

The proposed method is validated using simulations. The Terminal Maneuvering Area (TMA) of Barcelona-El Prat airport (IATA: LEBL, ICAO: BCN) is selected as scenario. The following particularities of this choice are noted:

- The airport lies in a coastal area, i.e., by the Mediterranean Sea. The propagation above the sea is considered obstacle-free which results in identical arcs (isolines) of attenuation levels for a relatively large region around the airport. The attenuation over this region does not differ much from a simple free-space path loss, thus complicating the task of resolving the localization of the RFI source.

- The runway configuration consists of two parallel runways to the sea and one additional runway perpendicular to it for arrivals only. Therefore, most of the arrival and departure procedures take place parallel to the coastline.
- Barcelona metropolitan region extends for more than 2,000 km². No significant obstacles other than moderate-to-tall buildings exist in this region which again implies that the path loss is relatively homogeneous in a large area.

A total of 4 SILENT nodes are considered in the simulations: 2 SILENT nodes lie inside the airport, while 2 in the vicinity of it (Table 1, Figure 8). An RFI source is located at coordinates (latitude, longitude) = (41.42669, 2.23554).

Table 1: SILENT nodes coordinates

SILENT	Coordinates WGS84 [deg]	Comments
1	41.29562, 2.09511	ATC tower
2	41.31117, 2.09215	Iberia's maintenance hangar
3	41.35789, 2.18527	Port facilities
4	41.41725, 2.11423	Collserola (TV/radio broadcasting tower)

For the scenario defined above, synthetic measurements of received signal power are generated for each of the SILENT nodes. Measurements include an additive Gaussian noise term of varying standard deviation (3 dB for close-range –in-airport– SILENT nodes, and 2 dB for the rest). A total of 1000 Monte-Carlo trials are run considering 300 power measurements (e.g., 5 minutes @ 1 Hz).

Figure 9 shows a histogram of the PDOA accuracy error when no angle-of-arrival information is used. It is defined as the Haversine distance between the estimated latitude and longitude of the RFI source, and the actual values of them. Moreover, Figure 10 shows a heatmap of the estimated RFI positions. Actual RFI location is marked with a diamond symbol. From the results, it is observed a relatively large concentration of points north-east of the RFI actual position.

The previous heatmap and histogram show that different clusters of potential localizations may result from employing 4 SILENT nodes only in a vanilla PDOA technique. Although most of them lie close to the actual position, it may become an inconvenience for mitigating it completely.

The fusion of angle-of-arrival information from SILENT nodes is intended to improve this result. Clearly, the addition of directional data (even with some degrees of uncertainty) may eliminate some of the previous number of clusters due to this a priori knowledge. To simulate this effect, each SILENT node is considered to provide an angle-of-arrival of the RFI source with its accuracy. These values result from solving the set of equations from the P&F algorithm (Section 5).

Figure 11 shows the histogram containing the PDOA accuracy error when using angle-of-arrival information. Clearly, there is a significant improvement with respect to Figure 9. Similarly, Figure 12 shows a heatmap with the resulting position estimates.

5.5 Assessment of Afflicted Airspace

When a spoofing attack is detected and accurately localized by VAULT, the airspace afflicted by it can be determined. To aid with this computation the system employs the SPLAT! tool [25] to

Figure 8: Top: SILENT nodes layout as viewed from the airport (no RFI). Middle: View of the airport from the RFI source. Bottom: Overlay of an instrument landing approach with the scenario. Map data: Google, Data SIO, NOAA, U.S. Navy, NGA, GEBCO, Landsat / Copernicus, Inst. Geogr. Nacional, Airbus, ENAIRE.

Figure 9: Realization of a histogram of PDOA accuracy error (no angle-of-arrival information).

Figure 10: Example of a heatmap containing the occurrences of the PDOA geolocation solution (1000 trials, no angle-of-arrival mask). Actual RFI location is marked with a diamond symbol.

perform point-to-point computations of path loss across the predefined en route or TMA routes. Another assumption that holds is that both emitter (jammer or spoofer) and receiver (user) have isotropic transmitting and receiving antennas.

The SPLAT! tool requires the NASA's SRTM Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the area of interest. The files used have been the 1-arcsecond version 3 variant, available at [26]. For latitudes exceeding the $\pm 60^\circ$ covered by the original SRTM mission, the alternative ALOS World 3D - 30m from JAXA, available at [27], has been used together with the GDAL [28] script converter for conversion to SRTM format. Comparisons between both elevation models using the original SRTM and the equivalent converted ALOS region show minimal discrepancies between the predicted path losses, with differences below 1 dB for the cases analyzed.

The system computes the point-to-point propagation for each point in the discretized flight procedures and reports the highest received power detected for every procedure, with the visual warning depending on a threshold (Figure 13). Both the discretization size and affliction threshold are user configurable. Results show a close resemblance with free-space-path-loss for points when no line-of-sight obstructions are present, and a drop of received power with terrain. Alternatively, an attenuation map from the source can be computed (Figure 13). Due to the associated computational cost, this approach is not advised for regular operation.

Figure 11: Realization of a histogram of PDOA accuracy error when using angle-of-arrival information.

Figure 12: Example of a heatmap containing the occurrences of the PDOA localization solution (1000 trials) with angle-of-arrival information. Actual RFI location is marked with a diamond symbol.

5.6 Jamming and Spoofing Detection Using AI

To further increase the radio frequency interferences (RFI) detection capabilities, VAULT encompasses two Artificial Intelligence (AI) modules, namely a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification module and a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model. The former is designed for jamming detection, while the latter is used for spoofing detection.

Machine Learning (ML) models have been largely proposed in literature, but still its application in the industry is limited. Authors in [29] propose a spoofing detector that employs an SVM model to classify the spoofed and authentic signals received by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). The work in [30] evaluate five learning models for GPS spoofing detection in UAVs. Similarly, the work in [31] evaluate SVM and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) performance under Amplitude Modulated (AM), Frequency Modulated (FM), chirp, Narrow Band (NB) and pulse jammers. The proposed method builds on top of the results obtained in [32].

Figure 13: Example of an attenuation map.

5.6.1 Jamming Detection Using SVM

GNSS receivers are designed to be robust against jamming RFI through the implementation of spread-spectrum CDMA signals, which provide significant processing gain against narrowband and low-power interference. However, GNSS signals are received at extremely low power, which makes GNSS receivers vulnerable to high-power AWGN-like jammers that floods the receiver frontend with noise. Continuous wave (CW) jammers also pose a threat, which despite having a narrowband spectral signature, can be highly effective if well aligned with the GNSS spectral characteristics [23].

Conventional jamming detection methods at the receiver side include simple pre-correlation techniques such as AGC monitoring or combination of AGC with other quantities as in Section 5.1, and post-correlation techniques involving C/N_0 monitoring, which are very effective against high power jamming attacks but are dependent on the scenario, requiring in-site calibration, where nominal AGC values are previously recorded to compare against incoming signal.

Contrary to statistical methods where RF and observable monitoring is used to find deterministic thresholds, SVM find intrinsic patterns hidden inside the signal's features and the relationship between them to determine whether the ingested signal is clean-only GNSS or jammed. As a supervised learning method, this technique requires previously labeled datasets containing both clean and RFI data to learn how to classify incoming signals. In this paper, the 3 dB bandwidth and the peak power measured at the GNSS receiver's frontend have been extracted as features to train the algorithm, since they exhibit differences between signal classes (i.e., clean and jammed signals). Specifically, signals coming from GNSS satellites present a known and stable bandwidth, while the signal reaching the receiver's frontend from jammer devices is typically higher in power with a clear signature in the spectrum in terms of occupied bandwidth.

5.6.2 Spoofing Detection Using VAE

An additional spoofing detection layer is presented in this paper: a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) model. VAE models are a type of unsupervised, deep generative models that employ potentially many convolutional layers to first compress the input signal into a reduced, more manageable latent space (the so-called encoder model), responsible for capturing essential features, and second to reconstruct the original signal based on these features (the decoder

model). Its basis is that it learns to reconstruct data similar to the data used during training (i.e., clean GNSS signals), while failing to accurately reconstruct data that presents distinct features (i.e., counterfeit signals) extracted in the latent space representation.

In brief, VAE models perform learning and inference using latent variables, typically denoted by \mathbf{z} , and utilizing an observed variable \mathbf{x} . The ultimate goal is to *learn* or approximate the (generative) underlying process to obtain the values \mathbf{x} by some model $p_\theta(\mathbf{x})$, with parameters θ . Moreover, the posterior distribution $p_\theta(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) = p_\theta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z})/p_\theta(\mathbf{x})$ —that includes the marginal probability of data under the model in the denominator—fully characterizes the model. However, learning of these posterior and marginal probabilities is intractable given the large dimensionality of the problem.

To solve the previous intractability, VAE models combine two ingredients [33]:

- Deep latent variable models that make use of (deep) neural networks to parametrize distributions, in particular conditional distributions (e.g., $p_\theta(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x})$), such that the neural networks output the distributional parameters over an input variable.
- Stochastic gradient descent that optimizes model parameters by randomly drawing batches of data $\mathcal{M} \subset \mathcal{D}$, where \mathcal{D} is a dataset containing N datapoints, i.e., $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(N)}\}$

The *encoder* model $q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$ with variational parameters ϕ is introduced such that:

$$q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) \approx p_\theta(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) \quad (19)$$

The distribution in Equation (19) can be parametrized using deep neural networks as well such that the variational parameters are to be estimated. The optimization objective that will determine the best choice of inference model is called the evidence lower bound or ELBO:

$$\begin{aligned} \log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}) = & \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})} [\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}) - \log q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})]}_{\text{ELBO}} \\ & + D_{KL}(q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x}) || p_\theta(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where the second term in Equation (20) is the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between $q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$ and $p_\theta(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$, i.e., the distance between the approximate posterior and the true posterior, which is non-negative and zero if, and only if, both are equal, and $\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x})$, the log marginal distribution over the observed variables.

Translating the previous model to an actual learning problem, datapoints \mathbf{x} belong typically to high-dimensional spaces. This is the case of images and the number of pixels as the dimensions. In a generative model, the distribution $p_\theta(\mathbf{x})$ is learned such that the new (unseen) samples drawn from that distribution match as possible the ones observed and generated by $p(\mathbf{x})$. The latent space of \mathbf{z} is obtained by mapping values from the dataset of observations \mathcal{D} to a new space using the encoder $q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$ and it is kept as "simple" as possible. In VAE models, this is typically achieved by using multivariate Gaussian distributions that propagate and transform to posteriors also as Gaussian [33].

In this paper, the spectrogram representation of L1/E1 and L5/E5 are utilized separately and divided into multiple images as part of the observations. The encoder and decoder neural networks are shown in Figure 14. It consists of different convolutional, pooling and up- and down-sampling layers. They are responsible for capturing nonlinearities, improving resolution (for the decoder) and dimensionality reduction of the features in the images. Figure 15 shows an example of a training spectrogram showing three distinct phases: clean-only GNSS signal, conducted jamming and clean-only signal again but with a different noise floor level.

Figure 14: Top: Encoder model. Bottom: Decoder model.

During prediction, new spectrogram images are input to the learned model. This will consist in reducing the input to the latent space dimensionality and the decoder model to reconstruct the original spectrogram. A reconstruction loss is computed using the mean squared error (MSE) as in e.g., [34] and it serves to detect anomalies in future observations with respect to the training set. Indeed, if the MSE is greater than a predefined threshold, the received signal is assumed to be spoofed as in Figure 16, i.e.:

$$\text{Threshold} = \mu_{\text{MSE}} + \gamma \sigma_{\text{MSE}} \quad (21)$$

where μ_{MSE} and σ_{MSE} are the mean and standard deviation of the MSE from the training set, and γ is a tunable scaling factor that controls the deviation from the mean reconstruction error required to classify an image as spoofed.

Figure 15: Dataset containing approx. 630 seconds of data. Clean-only GNSS signal ranges [0, 415] s, spoofing from [416, 566] and jamming for the rest of the dataset.

Figure 16: MSE between original and reconstructed images for the testing dataset. Jamming starts at the 416th sample and Spoofing at the 476th. The dotted red line indicates the detection threshold.

5.7 Augmented Detection

SILENT implements different layers of jamming and spoofing detection, namely the dispersion of double differences (D3) technique, AGC vs C/N_0 and C/N_0 vs elevation modules. The

output of these modules are a per-epoch (at a frequency of 1 Hz) flag indicating whether a jamming (or spoofing) event has been detected. A module combines all spoofing detection layers above in a novel logic to make a final decision whether the received signals are being spoofed or not.

The implemented logic is a Bayesian hierarchical model that builds on top of the idea that a decision about a parameter is made in terms of probability statements rather than on frequentist conclusions [35]. As an example, consider the problem of estimating the probability p that a Bernoulli experiment takes the value 1. Bernoulli experiments are random experiments with two possible outcomes: success and failure, such as in the case that a given epoch is experiencing spoofing. The parameter p could be estimated using a frequentist approach like, e.g., maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). However, a Bayesian framework is also a good approach to retrieve the underlying generating probability. The parameter under estimation is normally denoted as θ —instead of p —. More importantly, these probability statements are conditioned on some observations (e.g., a sequence of observed experiments that take values $[0, 1]$). Additionally, the hierarchical model exploits the fact that some hyperparameters involved are left to the model to be estimated or inferred using the observed data as well.

Applied to our case, the module will output the probability that a satellite is spoofed given the per epoch binary outputs of the detection layers AGC vs C/N_0 and the D3 module. The framework is flexible in the sense that it can be extended to as many detection layers as available whenever the same time base is available. However, no previous knowledge on the performance of the algorithms in terms of sensitivity and specificity is assumed. Sensitivity is the probability of a positive test or 0/1 experiment result given that the experiment takes actually a positive value, while specificity is the probability of a negative test result given that the experiment is actually negative. Leaving the sensitivity and specificity as hyperparameters is justified by the fact that for characterizing the performance of the C/N_0 vs elevation and the D3 modules, a large set of spoofing attacks shall be evaluated with varying power, characteristics, signal-to-spoofing ratios, etc. Since this is not feasible to be performed, this uncertainty is captured in the model as hyperparameters. Furthermore, literature has tackled the problem of unknown sensitivity and specificity in a similar fashion, i.e., using a Bayesian framework [36].

More formally, in Bayesian statistics, the main ingredients to perform inference can be reduced to the following:

- A prior distribution on the parameter θ referred to as $p(\theta)$.
- Observed data y .
- A sampling distribution $p(y|\theta)$ that quantifies how likely the data has been generated by θ . For that reason, it is often referred to as the likelihood function of the observed data.

Combining the previous, a posterior density $p(\theta|y)$ proportional to the previous terms, i.e., $p(\theta|y) \propto p(\theta)p(y|\theta)$ that exploits the Bayes' rule and performs inference on θ . The reader is referred to [35] for a detailed exposition of how the computation of a posterior is performed and its associated challenges. However, few aspects for proper inference are remarked here:

- The choice of the prior $p(\theta)$ is normally left to the modeller. The prior shall capture the distribution of the possible values θ , including the uncertainty that the modeller may have on them (or the a priori knowledge of it). When there is no previous knowledge about θ , a reasonable prior would be the uniform (non-informative) distribution, $p(\theta) \sim U(0, 1)$. However, informative priors may be more convenient and exploit the previous knowledge of the modeller or from past observed data. In turn, this reduces the uncertainty to be

propagated during the posterior computation since a non-informative prior may difficult this task of obtaining a reliable posterior value.

- The parameters of a prior distribution are often referred to as hyperparameters as already mentioned. Moreover, hyperpriors [37] refer to a prior distribution on a hyperparameter. For example, if a Beta distribution $Beta(\alpha, \beta)$ is used to model the distribution of the parameter p of a Bernoulli distribution, the Beta distribution is a prior distribution of p . However, hyperparameters α and β could be left with an associated prior in the model. These priors are referred to as hyperpriors.
- When computing the posterior distribution, the property of conjugacy plays an important role. While a formal definition is more elaborate and can be found in [35], it is referred to as the property that the posterior distribution follows the same parametric form as the prior distribution. This is a mathematically convenient property since a closed-form solution of posteriors can be obtained for analytical comparison and performance evaluation.

Once the ingredients and main properties of a hierarchical model are laid out, the proposed model for spoofing detection on a satellite basis is shown in Figure 17. The main components of the model are described next:

- The event that spoofing is present for each epoch is modelled as a Bernoulli distribution with prevalence (probability of success) as a hyperprior with Beta distribution. The number of epochs per satellite to be considered may vary depending on the different timestamps available for each satellite, i.e., detection layers have to be aligned and joined in their time base. SILENT nodes work on a near real-time with a snapshot of at least 30 seconds. However, this number may be considerably less if all algorithms have not detected the same number of satellites for the same number of epochs.
- Prevalence (denoted by θ) is modeled as a Beta distribution. This is justified by the following:
 - The Beta distribution is defined on the interval $[0, 1]$, the natural domain for prevalence.
 - The Beta distribution has a large flexibility since it can take both non-informative (uniform) shapes with $Beta(1, 1)$, low prevalence informative priors with $Beta(1, 10)$ or combined low and high informative prior with, e.g., $Beta(0.5, 0.5)$. This last case is of particular interest for spoofing determination since the prevalence is either low or high. In other words, a spoofing attack is either present or not, it does not make sense to have a prevalence of 0.5. Thus, a prior that balances both low and high confidence is chosen for our purposes.
 - The Beta distribution is the conjugate prior of a Bernoulli likelihood [35], so the Bayesian update (posterior computation) could be analytically solved.
- Similarly, since our knowledge on the sensitivity and the specificity of the C/N_0 vs elevation module and D3 technique module is limited or none, they are left as priors with a Beta distribution. For the latter, not only the D3 flag is used, but an intermediate variable that counts the number of cycle slips is included in the model. Thus, it accounts for 3 layers of detection to be fused in the hierarchical model. In all cases, the priors are set to informative with $Beta(5, 2)$. This choice is justified since the distribution skews towards values greater than 0.5 with a peak around 0.75. These values are reasonable to

expect in any moderate performing detection algorithm (sensitivity \sim specificity greater than 0.75). Otherwise, algorithms with lower values of sensitivity and specificity would be close to random choice algorithms. Our choice is conservative nonetheless.

Figure 17: Bayesian hierarchical model implemented in the augmented detection module.

The previous model was implemented and validated with synthetic data using the convenient library PyMC, a probabilistic programming framework built on Python that allows users to define Bayesian models using intuitive syntax and perform inference using methods like Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), variational inference, and more. Key to the implementation is the `PM.SAMPLE()` function that computes the posterior distribution numerically sampling efficiently from the provided priors and outputs. In our case, the posterior is averaged over all models to obtain a single metric, namely the posterior that a (spoofing) event is present given the algorithm outputs for a given satellite. However, this averaging may result in an inefficient estimate whenever one out of the two detection algorithms misbehave in terms of probability of detection and false alarm. Simulations used a prevalence of 0.9, a sensitivity of 0.75, and a specificity of 0.8. Sampling was done for 10000 iterations using 4 chains. Convergence was assured in all trials and estimated hyperparameters, namely specificity and sensitivity of the models, were close to simulated values.

5.8 Deployment Considerations

In any RFI monitoring solution, the number of monitoring nodes to be deployed and their position pose an optimization problem that shall balance cost, coverage/visibility, sensitivity or other aspects such as construction works restrictions. Dilution of Precision (DOP) relates the measurement error to the position error, i.e., how the changes in the observed or indirectly obtained quantities such as range, angle-of-arrival, etc., affect the positioning, geolocation, etc. It has been extensively used by the GNSS community to quantify the system positioning performance under different satellite visibility conditions. Indeed, GNSS perform indirectly a time-of-arrival (TOA) estimation to determine the position of a user. TOA systems measure the time-of-flight of a signal coming from different sources or satellites, as in the case of GNSS. Propagation times can be trivially converted into range information using the propagation speed, i.e., the speed of light. As a result, spheres centered at the sources and with radii equal to the ranges are formed, and their intersection determines the user position.

By contrast, angle-of-arrival systems employ the information of at least two angles or directions to a user to localize it. In this case, the observability matrix \mathbf{H} that relates the observed or measured angle with the positioning error is defined as [38]:

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{(y-y_1)}{r_1^2} & -\frac{(x-x_1)}{r_1^2} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -\frac{(y-y_n)}{r_n^2} & -\frac{(x-x_n)}{r_n^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

where:

- (x, y) is the actual position of the user.
- (x_i, y_i) is the position of the i -th SILENT nnode or station that performs the angle-of-arrival estimation.
- $r_i = \sqrt{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2}$ is the user-SILENT range.

If the standard deviations of measurements σ_ϕ from different SILENT nodes are equal, the GDOP can be easily computed as:

$$\sigma_p = \text{GDOP} \cdot \sigma_\phi = \sqrt{\text{trace}\left((\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H})^{-1}\right)} \cdot \sigma_\phi \quad (23)$$

The term GDOP from [Equation \(23\)](#) is used in a discretized region around Barcelona-El Prat airport scenario considered in the modified PDOA analysis ([Section 5.3](#)). The configuration of SILENT nodes is changed using either 4 or 3 nodes. The resulting GDOP is shown in [Figure 18](#). Clearly, the GDOP slightly degrades as the number of nodes decreases. The effect becomes more evident in the sections connecting pairs of SILENT nodes, where the angle-of-arrival information may be ambiguous. Since the maps are scaled down to $\sigma_\phi = 0.1$ rad (5.7 deg), the GDOP indicates directly the degradation in positioning in meters.

6 Validation

This section presents the validation and verification results obtained both SILENT and VAULT product concepts. The validation has been done in two sequential phases:

- During an initial phase (Phase I), most relevant SW modules for jamming and spoofing detection and localization were tested isolated in the lab. Both authentic (signal-in-space) and simulated GNSS signals were considered. The latter were simulated using Skydel GNSS simulator. The details of the simulated scenario are contained in [Table 2](#).
- The second validation phase (Phase II) took place during the Jammertest 2025 campaign, where jamming, spoofing and meaconing tests were conducted open air. A full model of the system working in real-time was deployed during the week-long event and put to use in a realistic operational environment.

6.1 Spoofing Detection and Localization Performance

During Phase I, GNSS signal-in-space was recorded, whereas spoofing was simulated and injected (conducted) to the COTS receivers, with GPS L1 C/A and L5 PRNs 13, 14 and 22 spoofed. [Figure 19](#) shows an example of the dispersion of the double differences (D3) obtained for one of the baselines. Grouped double differences indicate these PRN may be originated from

Figure 18: Top: GDOP ($\sigma_\phi = 0.1$ rad, 5.7 deg) using 4 SILENT nodes. Middle: same GDOP using 3 SILENT nodes only, where the redundant in-airport node is removed. Bottom: same as before but removing SILENT4 node.

Table 2: Simulated spoofing scenario

Parameter	Value
Constellations	GPS+Galileo
Bands	L1/L5 + E1/E5a
Spoofed PRNs (GPS)	13, 14, 22
Reference power	Default
Simulation date	23/02/2024 18:30:00 UTC
Sampling	25 Msps, 16 bits
Duration	180 s
Simulated coordinates	45.0000°, -73.0000°, 2.0 m

a single source, meaning that they may be spoofed. While PRNs 13, 14 and 22 are intentionally spoofed, PRNs 17 and 30 are mistakenly flagged as spoofed, as seen in Figure 20. In contrast, during nominal condition, the same baseline correctly marked almost all epochs as clean, except for some cycle clips (in blue) and one epoch marked as spoofed (in red) in Figure 21.

Figure 19: Pseudorange double differences for a baseline (GPS L1 C/A only).

For this scenario in particular, the algorithm performance could be evaluated in terms of probability of false alarm and probability of missed detection. While this is the traditional approach in signal detection theory, the task to characterize a spoofing detection algorithm in terms of probability of false alarm and probability of missed detection is more elaborate since it shall be done for different regimes of C/N_0 , spoofing-to-signal ratio, constellation characteristics (number of spoofed PRNs, geometry, ephemeris, etc.). The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve shall be ultimately obtained. However, the use of COTS receivers makes this task even more difficult since some receiver internals such as clock reset, AGC calibration and adjustments, etc., may lead to different acquisition and tracking conditions of the signal even for the same conducted scenario. This is one of the reasons why the sensitivity and specificity of the detection algorithms were left as hyperparameters in the proposed Bayesian fusion algorithm (Section 5.7).

During Phase I, the angle-of-arrival capabilities were characterized in two ways. First, a simplified SILENT node was deployed at GMV premises (Figure 22). GNSS signal-in-space only was recorded and the different line-of-sight of the satellites were computed. Secondly, a

Figure 20: Detection algorithm (D3) output with simulated spoofing. Top: GPS L1 C/A band. Bottom: GPS L5 band.

Figure 21: Detection algorithm (D3) output with authentic signal only. Top: GPS L1 C/A band. Bottom: GPS L5 band.

conducted spoofing scenario was used and the datasets from the COTS receivers containing the observables of interest were postprocessed and analyzed.

Figure 23 shows the performance of the implemented P&F algorithm during signal-in-space signal only. The skyplot displays the estimated position of each satellite against its actual position, which is retrieved from the navigation data. Clearly, elevation computation is approximately accurate for most of the satellites independently of their actual elevation. Azimuth error varies from few degrees up to 45 degrees. This performance is considered in alignment with previous measurement campaigns, and it is attributed to a poor setup in terms of multipath, uncalibrated antenna phase center offsets and overall receiver observables quality. Moreover, few L5 satellites are in use by the algorithm. Performance is expected to improve when more L5 satellites are considered valid during the processing.

Figure 24 shows the performance of the implemented P&F algorithm for the simulated spoofing attack. The performance in both azimuth and elevation estimation is remarkably good except for PRN 8 that presents a large azimuth offset. Elevation error is less than 17 degrees for the spoofed satellites, while azimuth error is reduced to less than 5 degrees.

Figure 22: Setup during authentic signal recording at GMV Barcelona.

6.2 Validation of AI Methods

For the SVM module, clean and conducted jammed signals were recorded for both training and test purposes during Phase I. Training and test datasets were constructed from the datasets in Table 3 and Table 4. Training and test flow is depicted in Figure 25. The algorithm first splits the training dataset into 2 parts: one for training and another for testing. The training is performed in steps, tuning hyperparameters and performing a cross-validation on each step to finally obtain the optimal estimator with the best accuracy score. The optimal estimator is used with the test dataset to validate how it performs on new data. The confusion matrix is plotted to check the probability of false alarm (P_{fa}) and miss detection (P_{md}).

Figure 23: Results of P&F algorithm for authentic signal only. Top: Elevation and azimuth estimation using dual-frequency (L1 and L5) data (3D mode). Middle: Azimuth-only angle-of-arrival estimation dual-frequency (L1 and L5) data (2.5D mode). Bottom: Azimuth-only using L1 data only (2D mode).

Figure 24: Results of P&F algorithm for simulated spoofing attack. Top: Elevation and azimuth estimation using dual-frequency (L1 and L5) data (3D mode). Middle: Azimuth-only angle-of-arrival estimation dual-frequency (L1 and L5) data (2.5D mode). Bottom: Azimuth-only using L1 data only (2D mode).

Figure 26 and Figure 27 show the train evaluation for L1/E1 and L5/E5, respectively. More precisely, it displays the use of the normalized 3 dB bandwidth and received peak power as features for both clean and jammed signals, the confusion matrix, the decision boundary that separates one class from the other, and the classification prediction on the test part, where the samples that were misclassified are shown in red. The separation between classes is more challenging in the L1/E1 band, as both bandwidth and maximum power exhibit close clusters for clean and jammed signals. Some outliers are present in the training classification results, where several epochs are labeled as jamming although being in the lower part of the maximum power axis. A plausible explanation is that the jammer stopped transmission for several seconds during the recording of the jamming dataset, leading to the mislabeling of some clean epochs as jammed. Nevertheless, by employing a non-linear decision boundary where samples inside the purple region are classified as clean and those in the yellow zone as jammed, the classifier achieves great performance, with a P_{fa} of 0.3% and a P_{md} of 0.2%. At the L5/E5 band, separation between classes was easy, mainly due to the narrower bandwidth of the jammer used. Thus, a simple, linear decision boundary is employed, correctly classifying all predicted samples of the test dataset.

Table 3: Characteristics of the clean and jamming datasets for L1/E1 band. CW: Continuous Wave. BLWGN: Band-Limited White Gaussian Noise

Clean dataset				
Duration (min)	Jammer Type	Gain (dB)	Center freq. (MHz)	BW (MHz)
30	–	–	–	–
Jamming dataset				
Duration (min)	Jammer Type	Gain (dB)	Center freq. (MHz)	BW (MHz)
30	CW	6	1575.42	–
30	CW	12	1575.42	–
30	BLWGN	12	1575.42	2
30	Chirp	12	1575.42	2

Table 4: Characteristics of the clean and jamming datasets for L5/E5 band

Clean dataset				
Duration (min)	Jammer Type	Gain (dB)	Center freq. (MHz)	BW (MHz)
30	–	–	–	–
Jamming dataset				
Duration (min)	Jammer Type	Gain (dB)	Center freq. (MHz)	BW (MHz)
30	CW	6	1176.45	–
30	CW	12	1176.45	–
30	Chirp	12	1176.45	2

Figure 25: SVM training and test scheme.

Figure 26: L1 SVM classifier training and evaluation results.

Figure 27: L5 SVM classifier training and evaluation results.

VAE only requires a clean dataset to be trained. Figure 28 shows both the training and prediction data used in the VAE model. The former consists of authentic (signal-in-space) signal captured at GMV premises using the setup shown in Figure 22 during Phase I. More precisely, the data from the 4 receivers are concatenated. Despite using identical receiver and antenna part numbers, a clear separation between them can be established based on the noise floor. The procedure is repeated for both L1/E1 and L5/E5. Similarly, the prediction data concatenates one snapshot of authentic signal with the simulated spoofed attack described in Table 2.

Figure 29 shows the resulting MSE for the L1/E1 and L5/E5 prediction data shown in Figure 28. The MSE loss computation is performed in images formed by 10 snapshots of the spectrogram. Clearly, an anomaly is detected at the end of the prediction spectrogram since index 38 in Figure 29 shows a sudden increase in the MSE due to overlapping epochs with both clean and spoofed signal, which is in accordance with the start of the spoofing at sample 380 (Figure 28). This transient behaviour disappears when the reconstruction error is based on spoofed signal only. However, the subtleties of the spoofer (e.g., different noise floor) are well captured by the decoder in terms of a slightly offset reconstruction error.

6.3 Integrated System During Jammertest 2025 Campaign

The Phase II of the validation took place in Andøya, Norway, during the Jammertest 2025 test campaign. SILENT nodes were put to the test with a long-week event with different jamming, spoofing and meaconing scenarios varying in sophistication, power and constellations being jammed and/or spoofed. Two SILENT nodes were deployed: one full-size model mounted on a metallic structure to mock up e.g., an airport frangible tower, and a second one mounted in tripods due to logistics limitations (Figure 30). Both of them ran the real-time operational SW developed in the framework of the project.

During many spoofing events, an initial visual inspection of the VAULT HMI showed a sudden increase of received power at the start of the RFI emission (Figure 31). Further analysis

Figure 28: From top to bottom: Training spectrogram L1/E1. Training spectrogram L5/E5. Predicted spectrogram L1/E1. Predicted spectrogram L5/E5.

Figure 29: MSE at the output of the decoder. Top: L1. Bottom: L5.

Figure 30: Top: SILENT 1 with the spoofing transmission source at the top of the black crane. Middle: SILENT 2. Bottom: Bird's eye view of the scenario. SILENT nodes marked in orange as 1 and 2. Spoofer is marked as using a red cross marker. Map data: Google, Airbus.

after the event at GMV premises confirmed the results. Moreover, the VAULT web panel indicated the spoofing attack successfully. This was indicated to the operator by marking some variables and PRNs (the ones detected as spoofed) in red as shown in Figure 32.

The top inset in Figure 32 is a snapshot of VAULT web panel during a coherent position spoofing attack from a stationary antenna using true satellite ephemeris but false and misleading GNSS PNT information, simulating a driving route where the starting spoofed PVT position was the Bleik community house parking lot, where SILENT 1 was located. Due to its proximity with the spoofed position, the PVT coordinates are marked in orange (i.e., PVT deviation detected) and the two pinpoint markers (one for the measured PVT and the other for the SILENT 1 coordinates) appear to be at the same position. The sky map shows the PRNs detected as spoofed in red, estimating an angle-of-arrival coming from the east (90°). AGC vs C/N_0 values are in the spoofing region of the graph. Localization was performed using the implemented 2D mode.

Figure 31: In-band channel power over time (left) and out-of-band received power (right). Top: L1/E1. Bottom: L5/E5.

Similarly, the middle inset in Figure 32 corresponds to a coherent position spoofing attack from a stationary antenna using true satellite ephemeris with false and misleading GNSS PNT information as well, simulating a flying helicopter over the sea where the spoofed PVT position was far away from the node location this time. The sky map indicates that the angle-of-arrival of the spoofing signal comes from the north-east, which is the correct angle-of-arrival as seen in the bird's eye view from Figure 30. Localization was performed using the implemented 2.5D mode.

Finally, the bottom inset in Figure 32 shows a coherent position spoofing attack from a stationary antenna using true satellite ephemeris once again and simulating drifting position by gradually changing the pseudorange values. The sky map indicates that the angle-of-arrival of the spoofing signal comes from the east and an elevation around $20\text{--}30^\circ$. The true elevation was analytically computed to be 25° . Localization was performed using the implemented 3D mode.

Further postprocessing of the previous recorded data confirmed the observed results. However, although the dispersion of the double differences did always match the expected behavior during a spoofing attack, the D3 algorithm did not always succeed in detecting it successfully in near real-time operation (e.g., Figure 33). The issue was attributed to a SW bug.

Figure 32: VAULT web panel during a spoofing attack. Top: Angle-of-arrival estimation module in 2D mode (azimuth-only, L1 only). Middle: Angle-of-arrival estimation module in 2.5D mode (azimuth-only, combined L1+L5). Bottom: Angle-of-arrival estimation module in 3D mode (azimuth and elevation).

Figure 33: Top: dispersion of double differences during a spoofing attack. Middle: wrong epoch classification in near real-time. Bottom: successful epoch classification in postprocessing.

For the validation of the AI methods, many jamming and spoofing tests confirmed the expected performance of the implemented methods. The SVM and VAE models further confirmed the spoofing detection as shown in Figure 34. SVM showed a clear change in the epoch classification plot, where the start of the spoofing attack is when the samples transition from green (clean) to red (spoofing). The VAE method also showed a transition in the MSE plot, where a higher MSE indicates the presence of an anomaly.

Figure 34: Prediction outcome for a L1-only spoofing plus meaconing test. Top: SVM panel. Bottom: VAE panel.

When it came to jamming, both SVM and VAE models did also a good job detecting the disturbances, as seen in Figure 35. The SVM panel showed the prediction result as "CLEAN" although a large number of epochs were predicted to be jammed (the red dots). This is attributed to the training data being recorded a priori in Barcelona, which did not reflect the nominal conditions of the Jammertest area in terms of noise floor, multipath, received power, etc. This behavior can be fixed by retraining the algorithm with in-site data plus setting a lower M-over-N threshold (i.e., the ratio of jammed epochs over the total to classify the batch as "jammed").

After successfully detecting a spoofing event, VAULT processed the data received from SILENT 1 and SILENT 2 to estimate more accurately the position of the spoofing source. For this purpose, VAULT combined the triangulation done with the angle-of-arrival estimates from both nodes, a PDOA using received power from both nodes as well, and a digital elevation model (DEM) of Andøya region to perform the geolocation.

In Figure 36, blue markers point the SILENT nodes position, green marker points the spoofer actual position, red marker points the spoofing source estimated position, and dashed lines and shadows represent the angle-of-arrival (including its uncertainty measurements) used to determine the triangulation polygon, drawn using red lines. The darkest area in the figure (i.e., the polygon) is the combination of five angle-of-arrival snapshots (one angle-of-arrival estimate every minute). This resulted in a Haversine distance of 0.5 km between the real position and

Figure 35: AI models prediction at the start of a jamming test: Top: SVM prediction on L1/E1 and L5/E5. Bottom: VAE model prediction on L1/E1 and L5/E5.

Figure 36: Spoofing source position estimation.

the estimated one. Considering all detected events and filtering out outliers, a mean Haversine distance of 3.43 km between the ground truth spoofing source position and the estimated one was achieved. Results could probably be greatly improved with finer angle-of-arrival measurements (with less uncertainty), which in turn could be improved with a better geometry and number of nodes.

7 Conclusions

This paper has presented two product concepts based on COTS components, namely SILENT and VAULT, to detect, localize and assess GNSS RFI impact in real time. The former is an RFI monitoring station expected to be deployed in dense networks given its cost-effectiveness. Moreover, the multi-layered algorithm structure has been shown to perform well in an operational environment, i.e., the Jammertest 2025. Similarly, VAULT employs promising AI techniques with retraining capabilities as new data is available that may benefit from an operator’s labeling and experience. Finally, the precise geolocation capabilities of VAULT combining PDOA and angle-of-arrival estimates from different SILENT nodes are pivotal to improve the localization performance and for mitigation purposes as shown via simulations.

During the validation and verification campaign, the tandem SILENT and VAULT displayed a remarkably good performance, even with only two SILENT nodes deployed during the tests. However, a more realistic deployment with many SILENT nodes could result in better geolocation results. However, the angle-of-arrival estimation in the elevation component showed low-to-moderate performance. This is attributed to the typical difficulties of a GNSS receiver to resolve the error terms in the elevation dimension due to all of them accumulating in the line-of-sight between satellites and the receiver.

Additionally, the current maturity of the products presented is recognized to be a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7, i.e., the test model has demonstrated the performance in an operational environment with a full representation of the components to be used in the actual system. Future improvements should therefore focus on expanding system capabilities beyond the minimal functional version validated to date.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the ESA's Navigation Innovation and Support Program (NAV-ISP) Element 2 initiative for its valuable contribution to the development of both SILENT and VAULT product concepts.

The validation phase of the STAGER project (NAVISP-EL2-170) was partially carried out at Jammertest 2025. We would like to acknowledge the work of the organizers of Jammertest 2025 (Norwegian Public Roads Administration, Norwegian Communications Authority, Norwegian Defence Research Establishment, Norwegian Metrology Service, Norwegian Mapping Authority, Norwegian Space Agency and Testnor) for arranging a live test environment with jamming, spoofing and meaconing of GNSS signals, their support with the logistics, and their hospitality during the event.

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